

Tracer Study on the Employment Status of Nueva ECIJA University of Science and Technology - Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Graduate from School Year 2017-2018

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Abstract:- This study aimed to determine if the field of specialization of the BSBA student of NEUST graduates and their academic-acquired skills and competencies are related to their present occupations. A modified Graduate Tracer Study (GTS) instrument was utilized to gather the quantitative data. Out of 584 total graduates only 38.18% respondent were administered, majority of the respondent are marketing graduates answered questionnaires representing College of Management and Business Technology. To locate the respondents, we used the probability of sampling. It is a method of sampling that utilizes some form of random selection. This research will trace Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology graduate from School Year 2016, their demographic profile and employment profile. The findings revealed that the graduates claimed that their knowledge, academic-acquired skills and competencies contributed greatly in their job performance. The results further proved that NEUST produces marketable and appropriately trained graduates with the majority landing in course-related jobs within a short period after graduation.

Keywords:- Graduate Tracer Study (GTS), skills, competencies, graduates, employability.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the aim of accomplishing the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology vision “The University envisions to be a recognized educational leader in Region III managed by committed and ethical public servants where a culture of excellence, high ethical standards and solidarity thrives and prospers in each of the University’s academic and administrative departments and units; and each college, institute and campus is a centre of development/excellence in instruction, research, extension, services, production, sports and cultural development, thereby transforming students, alumni and other clientele into high quality, competent and ethical leaders, professionals and/or middle level manpower in the fields of science, technology, education, management, arts and technology-based education and training.”, it is deemed necessary to know the present employability condition of the graduates.

The Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology is conducting a Graduate Tracer Study on the batch of 2016. The findings of this study will be beneficial to both the institution and its graduates. With this study, the institution can determine and show its effectiveness in creating highly competent graduates as an answer to the increasing technological competition. Likewise, this study can help assure the students that the school’s services do not end on their graduation day, but until they are given a better chance to land on a good job.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is to determine the employability of BSBA graduate student academic year 2018. Specifically, it seeks to determine the following:

- The profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - Sex;
 - Civil Status;
 - Present Location; and
 - Status of Employment.
- The Employment Profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - Present Occupation
 - Present Employment Status

III. METHODOLOGY

The researchers will make use of surveys to collect quantitative information about items in a population. Surveys of human populations and institution are common in political polling and government, health, social science and marketing research. A survey may focus on opinion or factual information depending on its purpose, and many surveys involved administering questions to individuals. The survey is a non-experimental, descriptive research method

To locate the respondents, the researchers will use the probability of sampling. It is a method of sampling that utilizes some form of random selection. In order to have a random selection method, you must set up some process or procedure that assures that the different units ‘in your population have equal probabilities of being chosen.

The researchers will trace Nueva Ecija University of Science And Technology graduate from School Year 2016, their demographic profile and employment profile.

IV. FINDINGS

The profile of the respondents in terms of:

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Female	176	78.92%
Male	47	21.08%
TOTAL	223	100%

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex

The Table 1 shows the Frequency Distribution of the respondents According to their Sex. These show that most of the respondents are female which has 78.92% and 21.08% are male.

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	220	98.65%
Married	3	1.35%
TOTAL	223	100%

Table 2: Distribution of the Respondents According to their Civil Status

The Table 2 shows the frequency distribution of the respondents According to their Civil Status. Out of 223 respondents, 98.65% are single and 1.35% are married.

The Employment Profile of the respondents in terms of:

Occupational Classification	Frequency	Percentage %
Entrepreneur	6	2.69%
Private Employee	169	75.78%
Government Employee	48	21.52%
TOTAL	223	100%

Table 5: Frequency Distribution of the Respondents According to their Occupational Classifications

The Table 5 shows the frequency distribution of the Respondents According to their Occupational Classifications. Out of 223 respondents who are employed, in the Government, 21.52% Entrepreneur; 2.69% are Private Employee is 75.78%.

Present Status	Frequency	Percentage
Regular/ Permanent	48	21.52%
Contractual/Temporary	169	75.79%
Self-Employed	6	2.69%
TOTAL	223	100%

Table 6: Distribution of the Respondents According to their Present Employment Status

The Table 6 show the frequency distribution of the presently employed respondents. Out of 223 respondents, 21.52% are regular/permanent employees; are temporary /contractual; 75.79% and 2.69% are self-employed.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researchers arrived with the following conclusions:

- Most of the respondents are female; it shows that they have the ability of finding a job faster.
- Most of the respondents are single; it means that majority of them has the opportunity to sustained their needs and their family as well.
- Most of the respondent is residing in Cabanatuan cities some of them are near in the municipalities.

Location	Frequency	Percentage%
City	195	87.44%
Municipality	28	12.56%
TOTAL	223	100%

Table 3: Distribution of the Respondents According to their Location

The Table 3 shows the frequency distribution of the respondents According to their Location. These show that most of the respondents are residing in the City (like: Cabanatuan City) which has 87.44% and 12.56% are residing in Municipalities (like: Sta. Rosa, Talavera and Zaragosa, Gapan).

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Employed	223	100%
Unemployed	0	0%
TOTAL	649	100%

Table 4: Distribution of Presently Status of Employment

The Table 4 show the frequency distribution of the presently employed respondents. Out of 223 respondents are all employed.

- The researchers concluded that most of the respondents were employed.
- Most of the respondent’s occupational classifications connected in the private companies, only few in the government and few had built their own business It is most likely for the graduates because they’re skills matched the job.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the researchers arrived with the following recommendations:

- The graduates should aim for reaching higher job position in their respective jobs, in order for them to be honoured that they are competing in the world of professional’s with excellence.

- The Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, Administrative Officials should organize seminars, lectures and trainings to the graduating students of the university focusing in finding jobs after college and through channelling to other departments of the government and other companies for helping the graduates finding their jobs after graduation.
- The batch 2016 graduates should always keep in touch so that they can inform their batch mates if there is a job opening for them.
- The graduates should value the competencies that they learned in college because it is going to be useful in the future.
- The Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology should have a website for the employment status of the graduates.

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